

Irish Research eLibrary

National Open Access Monitor Project

Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

This project has received funding from Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the Open Research Fund Call.

REPORT ON THE OUTCOME OF THE “NATIONAL OPEN ACCESS MONITOR SURVEY: DEFINING REQUIREMENTS”. DR CATHERINE FERRIS, PROJECT MANAGER, IREL. MARCH 2023

Table of Contents

Introduction	2
1. Scope	3
2. Validation and/or Expansion on NORF OA Monitor Policy Brief Documents.....	4
2.1 Success Criteria	4
2.2 User Personas	6
2.3 User Stories (Functional Requirements and Prioritisation)	7
3. Functional Requirements.....	9
Appendix 1	11
Appendix 2	14
Appendix 3	16
Appendix 4	17
Appendix 5	18
Appendix 6	23
Appendix 7	24

INTRODUCTION

The report contains the results and conclusions from the first stakeholder survey of the National Open Access Monitor Project, which was carried out between February 2-28th 2023. The purpose of this survey was to capture stakeholder input on the tender requirements for the National Open Access Monitor. The tender will be based on the specifications of the NORF [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030](#) (2022), NORF [National Open Research Landscape Report](#) (2021), [Science Europe's briefing paper on Open Access Monitoring](#) (2021), the NORF [Policy Brief on National Open Access Monitoring](#) (2021) and the [National Open Access Monitor Project Plan](#) (2022). Stakeholders, in this context, were defined in the widest sense: anyone with a role in currently or potentially monitoring open access to research publications in Ireland, or who will enable monitoring of open access in Ireland, or who will use the resulting open access Monitor, were invited to participate and contribute. A PDF of the survey is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588787>

Responses

The survey received 37 unique responses, from 30 organisations/groups/entities representing all stakeholder groups: government, research funding organisations, research performing organisations, service providers and others. Of those 30 organisations/groups/entities, 25 are listed as endorsing organisations of the NORF Action Plan: <https://norf.ie/national-action-plan/>

A note on pseudonymisation, transparency and reproducibility

Transparency is a core principle of this project, and therefore it was intended to capture contributor provenance at the outset: to capture *who/which entity* contributes *what* to the National Open Access Monitor Project, to enable all decisions made in the delivery of the Monitor to be transparent. All participants were asked to provide input and contribute as representatives of stakeholder entities and to provide explicit consent to identify their contributions, their names, their job titles and organisations. While pseudonymisation was offered for those who would rather their contribution was not publicly attributed to them, it was not anticipated that many contributors would avail of this option in this context. However, of the 37 respondents, 23 chose pseudonymisation and 14 chose to be identifiable. While this does not impact the results of the survey, it impacts the transparency of the conclusions drawn.

Oversampling

The survey was designed to enable multiple partial contributions from each stakeholder organisation/group/entity. Respondents were asked to complete the sections relevant to them/their role, to submit those answers, then to distribute the survey out to others within their organisation/entity/group so that they could fill in the sections relevant to them. As some stakeholder organisations/groups/entities chose to only submit one response, some submitted multiples, and not every respondent answered every question, a review of the response data was

carried out pre-pseudonymisation to assess for the impact of oversampling: the impact of one organisation submitting one response and one organisation submitting multiple responses. This review concluded that the survey conclusions remained the same if each organisation's responses were collated to be counted as one response, or if each respondent's response was counted as one response. This is not visible in the pseudonymised results as (a) stakeholder organisations/groups/entities are not identifiable and (b) not all contributors from the same organisations chose to be identifiable or not identifiable.

1. SCOPE

Conclusion

This section of the survey focused on arriving at a community-agreed definition on the scope of the National Open Access Monitor. The opening proposal was that the tender for the National Open Access Monitor specifies that the Monitor:

1. uses the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access"¹
2. uses the UnPaywall definition of "open access types"
3. initially focuses on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings
4. has the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during [Action 6.2.3](#), expected in 2025-2027)
5. focuses on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI
6. defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.

The logic for these proposals was detailed within the survey and respondents were invited to agree or disagree and propose an alternative.

Of the survey respondents that answered these scoping questions:

- 97% **agreed** with the use of the BOAI definition of "open access" for this purpose
- 94% **agreed** with the use of the UnPaywall definition of "open access types" for this purpose
- 97% **agreed** that peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings are initially prioritised in the tender requirements for the National Open Access Monitor; with the proviso that the Monitor must have

¹ "By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself." <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/>

the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during Action 6.2.3, expected in 2025-2027).

- 94% **agreed** that the National Open Access Monitor focus on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI
- 91% **agreed** that the National Open Access Monitor defines an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata.

Therefore, all proposals were passed with over 90% agreement. Dissenting opinions have been delineated and responded to in Appendix 1.

2. VALIDATION AND/OR EXPANSION ON NORF OA MONITOR POLICY BRIEF DOCUMENTS

This survey section focused on validating, and if required expanding on, the user stories and functional requirements of the National Open Access Monitor as identified by the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief Group:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588699>

Multiple responses from the same organisation/group/entity are treated as unique responses, as the survey structure invited self-categorisation under a secondary category, if applicable, in acknowledgement that organisations/groups/entities perform ranges of activities.

The responses have been analysed by the total number of respondents to the question (percentage of respondents that identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity) and by the stakeholder group which the KPI and/or Measure specified as relevant (percentage of respondents, self-categorised in a stakeholder group under Q6a and Q6ai, that identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity).² Responses by the designated stakeholder group(s) were prioritised. For inconclusive responses across those stakeholder groups, the total response was used. For statements without a designated stakeholder group, responses were weighted equally. Validation has been set as over 50%.

2.1 SUCCESS CRITERIA

Validation

- The sample size of respondents that answered this question: 34

² For the latter stakeholder group-based analysis, the same response may be counted twice, once the primary categorisation, and once in the second categorisation as it represents requirements by both stakeholder groups.

- The sample size of respondents, by stakeholder group:
 - Government: 3
 - Research funding organisation: 7
 - Research performing organisation: 24
 - Service provider (including research infrastructure): 7
 - Publisher: 4
 - Individual Contributor/Other: 2
- Publishers and Researchers (Individual Contributor/Other) are underrepresented in these survey responses, and therefore low response rates from these groups will not be considered as invalidation.
- See Appendix 2 for the point-by-point success criteria validation outcomes.

Expansion

Respondents were invited to indicate if none of the success criteria applied to their organisation/entity/group, and if this was the case, to describe the Success Criteria that best applied to their organisation/entity/group. No additional success criteria were provided by respondents.

Conclusion

Of the 12 success criteria documented in the appendix to the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief:

- 8 success criteria were deemed validated.
- 2 success criteria had insufficient respondent data to invalidate (due to stakeholder underrepresentation) and will be considered validated by default.
- 2 success criteria were not validated, with only 32% and 38% of respondents identifying these statements as best applying to their organisation/group/entity. These criteria are:
 - #9: Usage of portal interface (38%)
Web and/or COUNTER statistics indicating user engagement with the service
Must have
 - # 11: Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems (32%)
OA Monitoring cited as a source of data
Could have

Interpretation and Actions

#9: The NORF 2022 Open Research Fund proposal application form stated that 'Projects should also assess financial and operational sustainability beyond the duration of the project.'. As part of this assessment, the

Project will need to provide demonstratable evidence if the Monitor is being used, which will contribute to an evaluation of whether long-term financial investment is justifiable. The vendor will need to provide usage statistics to enable that determination. Therefore, this will be included in the tender as a requirement for the management of the Project.

#11: As nearly a third of respondents identified that this would be a success criteria for use of the Monitor, it will be included in the tender documentation. The success criteria was proposed as a “could have”, therefore it will **not** be a tender **requirement**, and will be accompanied with lower evaluation marking to reflect the balance within the responses.

2.2 USER PERSONAS

Validation

- The sample size of respondents that answered this question: 34
- The sample size of respondents, by stakeholder group:
 - Government: 3
 - Research funding organisation: 6
 - Research performing organisation: 22
 - Service provider (including research infrastructure): 7
 - Publisher: 3
 - Individual Contributor/Other: 2
- Publisher and Researchers (Individual Contributor/Other) are underrepresented in these survey responses, and therefore low response rates from these groups will not be considered as invalidation.
- See Appendix 3 for the point-by-point user personas validation outcomes.

Expansion

Respondents were invited to indicate if none of the user personas applied to their organisation/entity/group, and if this was the case, to describe a user persona that best applied to their organisation/entity/group. These responses are delineated in Appendix 4, with mappings to existing user personas.

Conclusion

Of the 7 user personas documented in the appendix to the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief:

- 4 user personas were deemed validated.

- 1 user persona had insufficient respondent data to invalidate (due to stakeholder underrepresentation) and will be considered validated by default.
- 2 user personas were not validated, with only 18% and 21% of respondents identifying these statements as best applying to their organisation/group/entity. These criteria are:
 - o Id F: OA Monitoring technical support/contact (21%)

This user has been assigned as technical support contact under the OA Monitoring governance structure. In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) ensuring the system is working as expected through monitoring tools etc.; b) being able to easily answer queries and complaints identified by other users. High
 - o Id G: External integrations (18%)

This is a third-party organisation or system. In using OA Monitoring, they are interested in harvesting records or subsets of records for inclusion in another resource or infrastructure. High

Interpretation and Actions

Id F: While only 21% of respondents have identified that this user story applies to their organisation/group/entity, the Project Manager will be required to provide technical support to stakeholder organisations and to easily answer queries and complaints identified by users, during this phase of the Monitor to successfully delivery the project. Therefore, it will be specified in the tender that the vendor must enable this, and this will be included as in the tender as a requirement.

Id G: This response aligns with the lower support for Success Criteria #11: *Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems (32%)*. This user story, supporting that success criteria, will be included in the tender but will not be a tender requirement, and will be accompanied with lower evaluation marking to reflect the balance within the responses.

Expansion of E: based on the additional user persona detail provided for E, the Frequency of Use for E will be updated from Low to Medium.

2.3 USER STORIES (FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS AND PRIORITISATION)

Validation

- The sample size of respondents that answered this question: 33
- The sample size of respondents, by stakeholder group:
 - o Government: 3
 - o Research funding organisation: 7
 - o Research performing organisation: 22
 - o Service provider (including research infrastructure): 7

- Publisher: 3
- Individual Contributor/Other: 1
- Publisher and Researchers (Individual Contributor/Other) are underrepresented in these survey responses, and therefore low response rates from these groups will not be considered as invalidation.
- See Appendix 5 for the point-by-point functional requirements validation outcomes.

Expansion

Respondents were invited to indicate if none of the user stories applied to their organisation/entity/group, and if this was the case, to describe the user story that best applied to their organisation/entity/group. Two additional user stories have been provided. These are delineated and responded to in Appendix 6.

Conclusion

Of the 22 user stories documented in the [appendix to the NORF OA Monitoring Policy Brief](#):

- 17 user stories were deemed validated.
- 1 user story had insufficient respondent data to invalidate (due to stakeholder underrepresentation) and will be considered validated by default.
- 4 user stories were not validated, with between only 18% and 48% of respondents identifying these statements as best applying to their organisation/group/entity. These criteria are:
 - #10: Bibliometric indicators (48%)

As a repository support officer/analyst/repository manager/researcher, I would like to see bibliometric indicators (e.g., Altmetric, Plum analytics, etc.) when searching for material
 - #14: Uptime monitoring/ alerting (18%)

As the technical contact, I want to be alerted when the system is unavailable and be able to review availability of the system over time.
 - #15: Harvest metadata via OAI-PMH (36%)

As a downstream aggregator, I want to be able to harvest metadata records or filtered
 - #21: System status page (33%)

As an end-user of the system, I want to be able to access a page which displays the current availability of the system as well as history of system availability over the previous month or year, e.g. <https://status.bitbucket.org/> or <https://status.github.com>.

Interpretation and Actions:

#10: As nearly half of respondents identified that this would be a user story for use of the Monitor, it will be included in the tender. The user story was proposed as a “could have”, therefore it will not be a tender requirement, and will be accompanied with lower evaluation marking to reflect the balance within the responses.

#14: Uptime monitoring/alerting for technical contacts will be required by the Project Manager to manage the vendor contract, and therefore this will be included in the tender as a requirement.

#15: The low demand for this functionality reflects the lower support for Success Criteria #11: *Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems (32%)* and User Persona id G: *Id G: External integrations | This is a third-party organisation or system (18%)*. This user story, supporting that success criteria, will be included in the tender but will not be a tender requirement, and will be accompanied with lower evaluation marking to reflect the balance within the responses.

#21: Only 33% of survey respondents identified that availability to a page which displays the current availability of the system as well as history of system availability over time, therefore this will not be included in the tender.

Updates to #5: “As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green-vs- Gold) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories-vs- preprint servers-vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions”

- based on feedback in the scoping section regarding the lack of clarity regarding Diamond OA, User Story 5 will be updated to “As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green-vs- Gold, Diamond) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories-vs- preprint servers-vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions”
- based on the specific reporting requirements in the Current and Future Functional Requirements relating to open access publishing agreements, Use Story 5 will be further updated to ““As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green-vs- Gold, Diamond), open access publishing agreements, and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories-vs- preprint servers-vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions”.

3. FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Questions 86-147 of the survey focused on further defining the functional requirements for the National Open Access Monitor, to explicitly define current OA reporting metrics for each stakeholder and required data points. Future functional requirements were captured in questions 148-210.

As stated in the survey text, “as per NORF requirements, all data supporting the National Open Access Monitor must be open under open licenses (e.g. CC0, CC-BY, ODC-BY), and therefore it may not be feasible for the National Open Access Monitor to include all data sources currently being used [or intending to be used] for open access monitoring and/or reporting. The intention in capturing this information is to understand current practice.”

The survey responses are delineated in appendix 7. These will be provided as an appendix to the tender, for the information of the vendor(s), to support their understanding of current practice and specific stakeholder expectation on the functionality of the Monitor.

While the vendor(s) will not be expected to deliver functionality that negates the need for any analysis work by stakeholders, they are expected to deliver on the project objective, which is to reduce the need for the current disparate practices and enable consistent transparent sector-wide analysis, as stated in the [Project Plan](#):

“As Ireland moves into the next phase of the NORF National Action Plan for Open Research, it is imperative to determine the current state of OA in Ireland, and to monitor how this develops as DFHERIS and NORF investment transitions Irish research towards open research. While such analysis is currently underway throughout the sector, it is resource-heavy, time-consuming and often-times dependent on proprietary data sources which leads to silos of data and analysis for single stakeholder benefit. This IReL proposal aims to rectify that. First, by identifying potential vendors and working to pilot and test potential solutions for the National OA Monitor. Then, by rolling out the approved solution(s) that will be publicly accessible to view and analyse, and be built based on community requirements.”

Appendix 1 delineates and responds to the dissenting opinions to the survey scoping section (questions 51-70)

51. DO YOU AGREE WITH THE USE OF THE BOAI DEFINITION OF "OPEN ACCESS" FOR THIS PURPOSE?

ANSWER: NO

52. Your preferred definition of "open access" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: Berlin Declaration

53. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "open access" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: I would expect that National OA monitoring would need to align with PlanS Principles which refer to the Berlin Declaration. It would be good to clarify what any deviation would mean for Irish Funders, and to clarify and understand why the National Open Access Plan has introduced this change. I accept that there may be good reasons for the change, and also that the existing HRB OA policy aligns to the Budapest initiative. Looking for understanding and also reassurance that there will be no unintended consequences here.

54. A link to the source of this definition of "open access"

1000686-1000668-106360674: https://openaccess.mpg.de/67605/berlin_declaration_engl.pdf

As [per Success Criteria #3](#) "Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to promote/enable OA compliance", the National Open Access Monitor must enable stakeholders to monitor compliance as per their specific, different compliance requirements (including PlanS). The use of the wider BOAI definition of open access intends to enable this.

55. DO YOU AGREE WITH THE USE OF THE UNPAYWALL DEFINITION OF "OPEN ACCESS TYPES" FOR THIS PURPOSE?

ANSWER: NO

56. Your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

57. The reason this is your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: Looking for reassurance that the OA types and licences align with PlanS. Checking with HRB Open Research colleagues how our publications on the platform would be categorised within the Unpaywall definitions, most likely Gold OA. Find the Unpaywall definitions very American e.g. 'toll-free'. Will the National OA monitor be able to differentiate between immediate and non-immediate OA?

58. A link to the source of this definition of "open access types"

1000686-1000668-106360674: <https://hrbopenresearch.org/>

Confirming that Plan S utilise the UnPaywall definitions: <https://www.coalition-s.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Plan-S-Annual-Report-2022.pdf> (page 10)

56. Your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106431246: I agree with the Unpaywall definition but would like the following distinction added to provide clarity and nuance between Pure Gold OA and Diamond OA. 'Diamond' Open Access refers to a scholarly publication model in which journals and platforms do not charge fees to either authors or readers."- Action Plan for Diamond Open Access

57. The reason this is your preferred definition of "open access types" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106431246: It's important for us as a community to be able to identify where publications come from. Diamond OA is distinct from what is commonly understood in the community by Gold OA and as the Diamond OA Action Plan states, "Diamond Open Access journals represent community-driven, academic-led and-owned publishing initiatives. Serving a fine-grained variety of generally small-scale, multilingual, and multicultural scholarly communities, these journals and platforms embody the concept of bibliodiversity." It is also an OA type that is widely supported and driven by libraries and we should be able to report on this impact. Finally, being able to determine where and how money is being spent on OA in a national context is something we as stakeholders and project drivers should be able to account for.

58. A link to the source of this definition of "open access types"

1000686-1000668-106431246: <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/action-plan-for-diamond-open-access/?fromprevious=20098>

Clarifying that as per the UnPaywall definition, Diamond OA journals will be classified as Gold OA Journals. Use of this definition does not preclude the Monitor from identifying Diamond.

User Story 5 states “As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green -vs- Gold) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories-vs- preprint servers-vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions”. The wording of User Story 5 will be updated to specify Diamond OA.

59. DO YOU AGREE THAT PEER-REVIEWED JOURNAL ARTICLES AND CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS ARE INITIALLY PRIORITISED IN THE TENDER REQUIREMENTS FOR THE NATIONAL OPEN ACCESS MONITOR; WITH THE PROVISO THAT THE MONITOR MUST HAVE THE POTENTIAL IN THE FUTURE TO EXPAND TO MONITOR MONOGRAPHS, BOOK CHAPTERS, OTHER SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION OUTPUTS, OPEN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES AND MEASURES (TO BE DEFINED DURING ACTION 6.2.3, EXPECTED IN 2025-2027)

ANSWER: NO

60. Your preferred list of publication types to be initially monitored by the National Open Access Monitor

1000686-1000668-105972140: Yes we agree with what has been proposed but we would like a timeframe by which all research outputs will be included.

61. The reason these publication types are your preferred types to be initially monitored by the National Open Access Monitor

1000686-1000668-105972140: We include all types of research outputs in [redacted], as do the other [redacted]. Traditional peer-reviewed literature only represents 25% of our research output.

62. A link to a source providing more information about this preference (if applicable)

1000686-1000668-105972140: [blank]

The [National Action Plan](#) states that Action 6.2.2. “Establish a national, high-level working group to make recommendations on the design and implementation of a national research reporting, monitoring and evaluation system that enshrines open research principles and aligns with international best practice” will be completed by 2024 and Action 6.2.3. “On the basis of recommendations made, expand the national monitor to encompass further aspects of open research activity and measures relevant to the national context. This may include indicators related to FAIR data, policies and societal impact” will be completed by 2027. Additional development of the Monitor beyond what is initially contracted for under this phase will be dependent on additional investment.

63. DO YOU AGREE THAT THE NATIONAL OPEN ACCESS MONITOR FOCUS ON PUBLICATIONS WHICH CAN BE UNIQUELY AND UNAMBIGUOUSLY IDENTIFIED BY A DOI?

ANSWER: NO

64. Your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

1000686-1000668-105972140: Use a range of identifiers including ISBN (despite issues), URLs and DOI

65. The reason why this is your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

1000686-1000668-105972140: I would be concerned that limiting to DOI would hamper the inclusion of other output types. Including other types of identifier is more challenging but also more inclusive.

66. Link to sources providing more information about this methodology

1000686-1000668-105972140: [blank]

In line with Question 59, the Monitor “must have the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures” and therefore must have the potential to uniquely and unambiguously identify those other publication outputs, at that time.

64. Your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

1000686-1000668-106040673: DOIs, Handles

65. The reason why this is your preferred method for the National Open Access Monitor to uniquely identify publications

1000686-1000668-106040673: Some peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings in the Institutional Repository have DOIs. All peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings, book chapters in the Institutional Repository have handles.

66. Link to sources providing more information about this methodology

1000686-1000668-106040673: [blank]

As documented in the [National Open Access Monitor Project Plan](#), metadata enrichment will be specifically actioned as part of the project. Implementation Workplan #12 states: “Work with vendor to identify sources for improvement and data enrichment. Identify and document actions required to enable data validation and enrichment. Work with project stakeholders (as specified in #1), together with all interdependent entities (vendors, service providers, PID providers, publishers, etc) to systematically and sustainably improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard.”

67: DO YOU AGREE FOR THE NATIONAL OPEN ACCESS MONITOR DEFINES AN "IRISH SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION" AS A PUBLICATION WHICH CONTAINS THE UNIQUE PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER OF AN IRISH ORGANISATION IN THE PUBLICATION AND/OR THE PUBLICATION METADATA AND/OR THE PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER METADATA?

ANSWER: NO

68. Your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-105501472: [blank]

69. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-105501472: We think the proposed definition may be limiting as many publications rather than including a PID for the institution, instead include the name of the institution in text and or the PID for the authors which can be linked back to the institution. We feel a broader definition of Irish Scholarly Publications may be beneficial.

70. A link to the source of this definition of "Irish scholarly publication" which is applicable to this context

1000686-1000668-105501472: [blank]

68. Your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: Comment: Ideally, agreed with the proposed definition but can I check what % of Irish publications would be currently included/ excluded in the proposed definition of "Irish scholarly publication"?

69. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

70. A link to the source of this definition of "Irish scholarly publication" which is applicable to this context

1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

68. Your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-105972140: I'm not certain of the maturity of the infrastructure around organisational and funding identifiers, I would have concerns about relying entirely on these IDs. String matching could also be explored.

69. The reason why this is your preferred definition of "Irish scholarly publication" for this purpose

1000686-1000668-105972140: The infrastructure for Org and funding IDs is immature compared with publications and may not be comprehensive.

70. A link to the source of this definition of "Irish scholarly publication" which is applicable to this context

1000686-1000668-105972140: [blank]

This is acknowledged and will be actively worked on as part of the project as instructed by the [NORF 2022 Open Research Fund Call for Expressions of Interest \(EOIs\)](#) documentation:

- "Document challenges that should be addressed in long-term monitoring solutions and recommend steps to be taken, including workflows for data validation and enrichment.
- Work to improve the quality and depth of data used for the national dashboard in line with international best practice through stakeholder collaboration with institutions, funders etc. and direct input or validation where possible."

It is unknown at this point what percentage of Irish publications would be included/excluded, but this will be actioned under [Implementation Workplan #11](#): "work with stakeholders to identify gaps, incomplete representation, or errors in pilot data."

Appendix 2 details the survey validation outcomes for the Success Criteria section, questions 71-74

Original Policy Brief				Survey Validation Outcomes		
#	KPI	Measure	Importance	% of respondents who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity	% of respondents, self-categorised in a stakeholder group under Q6a and Q6ai, who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity	Conclusion
1	Usage by Irish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) to measure funded research outputs	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have	82%	RFO: 100% RPO: 79%	Validated
2	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to measure OA	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data, e.g. the “% of publications deposited in Open Access repositories” KPI in the 2018-2020 Higher Education System Performance Framework	Must have	76%	RFO: 86% RPO: 75%	Validated
3	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to promote/enable OA compliance	Public documentation detailing how OA Monitoring is used to verify RPO/RFO OA policy, with corresponding instructions for their funded researchers	Must have	79%	RFO: 100% RPO: 79%	Validated
4	Usage by Irish national consortia to inform new OA publishing agreements, and monitor existing agreements	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data		47%	Consortia: 100%	Validated
5	Usage by government departments to measure and report on OA compliance as overall % of Irish research publications	Reports produced by Government Departments (e.g. DBEI, Education) and figures fed into E.U. reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have	59%	Government: 100%	Validated
6	Demonstrable engagement by researchers in	Documentation on RFO websites guiding researchers to OA Monitoring for	Must have	74%	Individual contributor/Other: 0%	Insufficient data

	using OA Monitoring when assessing their OA compliance	assessment/evidence of OA compliance				
7	Demonstrable use of OA Monitoring to inform and support strategic developments in the area of Open Science	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data or statistics in national reports or working groups, e.g. NORF or equivalent	Must have	65%	n/a	Validated
8	Usage by publishers to monitor visibility of published content and analyse sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	OA Monitoring cited as source of data		21%	Publisher: 50%	Insufficient data
9	Usage of portal interface	Web and/or COUNTER statistics indicating user engagement with the service	Must have	38%	n/a	Not validated
10	Integration of OA Monitoring data into RFO or RPO systems through API etc.	E.g. documented examples/case-studies of direct integration with RFO grant management systems or processes, RPO CRIS systems or process, RPO Institutional Repository systems, other Irish repositories, or processes	Should have	65%	RFO: 71% RPO: 67%	Validated
11	Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data.	Could have	32%	n/a	Not validated
12	Active, ongoing engagement among stakeholders	This is a rapidly evolving area, with new datasets and services becoming available every year. A key indicator of the success of OA Monitoring will be the extent to which stakeholders are engaged and the system is responsive to improvement and critical evaluation through successive, continuous iterations. In addition to more formal feedback from broader stakeholders,	Must have	71%	n/a	Validated

Appendix 3 details the survey validation outcomes for the User Personas section, questions 75-79

Original Policy Brief					Survey Validation Outcomes		
<i>Id</i>	<i>Persona/Role</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Motivation</i>	<i>Frequency of Use</i>	<i>% of respondents who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity</i>	<i>% of respondents, self-categorised in a stakeholder group under Q6a and Q6ai, who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
A	Policy strategist/analyst	This user works in one of the Irish RFOs, national consortia, or government departments.	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with national-level statistics and monitoring of research outputs and open access in order to inform strategic direction in relation to funding, impact assessment, publisher negotiations, transformative agreement monitoring, and Open Science/Access	Medium (Biannual reporting, reasonably regular checks on performance or on-demand querying)	35%	Government:100% RFO: 100% Consortia: 100%	Validated
B	Research support officer/analyst	This user works in the research support service or library of an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring national-level visibility of institutional research and in analysing their institution's OA performance relative to peer institutions, and in establishing compliance with RFO policies	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)	59%	RPO: 91%	Validated
C	Repository Manager	This user is responsible for managing a publications repository at one of the Irish RPOs	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring OA publications from their system are accurately reflected.	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)	59%	RPO: 86%	Validated
D	Individual researcher	This user is a researcher working at an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) establishing whether their publications are in compliance with the policies of their RFOs and RPO; b) ensuring their research outputs are visible at a national level;	Low (On-demand querying prompted, for example, by funding reporting or quality review process)	62%	Individual Contributor: 100%	Insufficient data

				Low individual usage but lots of individuals			
E	Publishers	Publishers, aggregators and related service providers	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring visibility of published content and in analysing sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	Low	21%	Publisher: 100%	Validated
F	OA Monitoring technical support/contact	This user has been assigned as technical support contact under the OA Monitoring governance structure	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) ensuring the system is working as expected through monitoring tools etc.; b) being able to easily answer queries and complaints identified by other users	High	21%	n/a	Not validated
G	External integrations	This is a third-party organisation or system	In using OA Monitoring, they are interested in harvesting records or subsets of records for inclusion in another resource or infrastructure	High	18%	n/a	Not validated

APPENDIX 4

Appendix 4 delineates and responds to the Other User Personas provided by respondents under questions 75-79

USER PERSONAS: IF YOU SELECTED OTHER, PLEASE DESCRIBE THE USER PERSONA THAT BEST APPLIES TO YOUR ORGANISATION/ENTITY/GROUP. PLEASE USE THE SAME FORMAT OF PERSONA/ROLE, DESCRIPTION, MOTIVATION, FREQUENCY OF USE.

76: Persona/Role

1000686-1000668-106360674: Owner of OA Publication Platform

77: Description

1000686-1000668-106360674: www.hrbopenresearch.org

78: Motivation

1000686-1000668-106360674: On a very practical level HRB Open Research can guarantee that it's publications are fully open and immediate without the need to put in place in-house extensive monitoring processes, that eligibility can be extended beyond our individual awards and aligned with our researchers, that we can fund beyond the legal term of a grant (knowing that the majority of publications happen at the end or during the post award period), and that we can support our researchers to publish a full range of research outputs beyond traditional articles, and eith [sic] an open peer-review model and linked underlying data/ This process is all achieved with minimum added administration, with reduced costs relative to typical APCs and with no reference to Impact Factors.

79: Frequency of Use

1000686-1000668-106360674: Monthly meeting with publisher

This user persona can be mapped to E above. Once E is met, this user persona requirement will be met. Based on this response, the Frequency of Use for E will be updated from Low to Medium.

76: Persona/Role

1000686-1000668-106465718: Research Funding Manager / Administrator

77: Description

1000686-1000668-106465718: This user works in one of the Irish RFOs

78: Motivation

1000686-1000668-106465718: To monitor OA availability of funded research

79: Frequency of Use

1000686-1000668-106465718: Medium (reasonably regular checks)

This user persona can be mapped to A above. Once A is met, this user persona requirement will be met.

APPENDIX 5*Appendix 5 details the survey validation outcomes for the User Stories section, questions 80-85*

Original Policy Brief						Survey Validation Outcomes		
#	Title	User Story	Personas	Importance	Category	% of respondents who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity	% of respondents, self-categorised in a stakeholder group under Q6a and Q6ai, who identified that the statements best applied to their organisation/group/entity	Conclusion
1	Identify % of current OA availability	As an analyst, I want to be able to easily identify the % of Irish peer-reviewed publications that are Open Access	A,B,C	Must have	Reports	73%	Government: 100% RFO: 100% RPO: 68% Consortium: 100%	Validated
2	Identify OA progress over time	As an analyst, I want to be able to compare the % of OA publications against historical 6 month or yearly snapshots to gauge progress towards OA (to gauge progress over time, you can't simply look at OA availability by year of publication)	A,B,C	Must have	Reports	73%	Government: 100% RFO: 86% RPO: 68% Consortium: 100%	Validated

3	Predefined/ Dashboard metrics	As a policy strategist/ analyst/ repository manager/ member of the public, I want to be presented with a visual dashboard of the most common statistics, including a) overall record count; b) overall Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown; c) Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown by year; d) overall breakdown by publication type; e) overall and OA breakdown by funder; f) overall and OA breakdown by institution; overall and OA breakdown by publisher	A, B, C, E	Should have	Reports	85%	Government: 100% RFO: 86% RPO: 91% Consortium: 100% Publishers: 100%	Validated
4	Faceted analysis drill-down functionality	As an analyst/ policy strategist/ researcher, I want to be able to easily visualise the OA % for publications by a number of facets including funding agency, Irish HEI, corresponding author affiliation, by year of publication, by a given subject or keyword, by publisher, by grant award ID, or an arbitrary combinations of these.	A,B,C,D	Must have	Functionality	79%	Government: 100% RFO: 86% RPO: 86% Consortium: 100% Individual Contributor: 0%	Validated
5	Evaluate performance of different OA strategies	As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green -vs- Gold) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories -vs- preprint servers - vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions	A,B	Should have	Reports	64%	Government: 67% RFO: 43% RPO: 73% Consortium: 100%	Validated
6	Export OA classification for further analysis	As an analyst, I want to be able to export item-level OA classification data (DOI, Title, OA	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data	70%	Government: 67% RFO: 57% RPO: 77% Consortium: 100% Individual Contributor= 0%	Validated

		Classification) for further analysis, either the entire dataset or for specific search results/filters (funder/institution/year/keyword, corresponding author affiliation/publisher/publication type etc.)						
7	Compare custom publication set	As an analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I want to be able to upload a list of DOIs and have the system return a report indicating a) whether the DOI is in OA Monitoring; b) the OA classification assigned by OA Monitoring	A,B,C,D	Nice to have	Data	56%	Government: 0% RFO: 43% RPO: 68% Consortium: 100% Individual Contributor: 0%	Validated
8	Grant reporting and assessment	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to be able to co-locate publications that have been funded by grants via my organisation/ agency/ department, for reporting.	A,B	Nice to have	Report	64%	Government: 67% RFO: 100% RPO: 68% Consortium: 0%	Validated
9	API Integration	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to easily extract data from OA Monitoring regarding material that's been uploaded in OA repositories for incorporation in my organisation's/ department local system, preferably via an API.	A,B	Should have	Data	58%	Government: 33% RFO: 71% RPO: 59% Consortium: 100%	Validated
10	Bibliometric indicators	As a repository support officer/ analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I would like to see bibliometric indicators (e.g., Altmetric, Plum analytics, etc.) when searching for material.	D	Could have	Functionality	48%	Government: 33% RFO: 29% RPO: 64% Consortium: 0% Individual Contributor: 0%	Not validated
11	Standardised usage statistics	As a repository manager, I would like to be able to easily see standardised local usage statistics for material accessed and downloaded from my repository via OA Monitoring.	B,C	Could have	Report	55%	RPO: 68%	Validated
12	Standardised COUNTER compliant	As a repository manager I would like to be able to see	B,C	Could have	Report	48%	RPO: 68%	Validated

	statistics	COUNTER compliant usage statistics for activities like searches and click-throughs.						
13	Author disambiguation	As an analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I want to see all publications by specific authors regardless of variant name forms and affiliation.	A,B,C,D, E	Should have	Functionality	67%	Government: 67% RFO: 86% RPO: 77% Consortium: 0% Publisher: 100% Individual Contributor: 0%	Validated
14	Uptime monitoring/ alerting	As the technical contact, I want to be alerted when the system is unavailable and be able to review availability of the system over time	F	Must have	Operational	18%	n/a	Not validated
15	Harvest metadata via OAI-PMH	As a downstream aggregator, I want to be able to harvest metadata records or filtered	G	Could have	Functionality	36%	n/a	Not validated
16	Documentation	As any user of the system, I want to be able to find succinct but complete documentation regarding: a) what records are contained; b) the criteria for selecting these records; c) the sources from which the records were derived; d) the criteria for open access classification; e) the method of open access classification; f) the governance and history of the system	A,B,C,D, E, F, G	Must have	Documentation	79%	n/a	Validated
17	Transparent feedback loop regarding functionality	As a user of the system, I want to be able to report an issue with a technical aspect of the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in a way that other users can see, e.g. public issue tracker or mailing list	A,B,C,D, E,G	Must have	Operational	61%	n/a	Validated
18	Transparent feedback loop regarding data	As a user of the system, I want to be able to query or report an issue with the data displayed in the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in	A,B,C,D, E,G	Must have	Operational	64%	n/a	Validated

19	Sync with ORCID	As an Irish researcher, I want to be able to sync all works listed in my ORCID profile with an OA monitoring system, ensuring they are indexed and available in the system and as a means of having control over how my work is represented in the national portal	D	Could have	Functionality	61%	Individual Contributor: 0%	Insufficient Data
20	Periodic data dumps	As an analyst/repository manager/researcher, and in absence of an API or other UI features which allow dynamic access to underlying data, I want to be able to access periodic data dumps/snapshots of included records and their OA classification for further offline analysis, e.g. one every 6 months	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data	55%	Government: 33% RFO: 57% RPO: 59% Consortium: 100% Individual Contributor: 0%	Validated
21	System status page	As an end-user of the system, I want to be able to access a page which displays the current availability of the system as well as history of system availability over the previous month or year, e.g. https://status.bitbucket.org/ or https://status.github.com	A,B,C,D, E,F,G	Could have	Operational	33%	n/a	Not validated
22	Embargoed access	As an analyst/repository manager/aggregator, I would like to be able to see the % of closed access records which have been deposited in a repository but which are currently embargoed	A,B,C,G	Should have	Data	76%	Government: 33% RFO: 57% RPO: 86% Consortium: 0%	Validated

Appendix 6 delineates and responds to the Other User Stories provided by respondents under questions 80-85

USER STORIES (FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS AND PRIORITISATION): IF YOU SELECTED OTHER, PLEASE DESCRIBE THE USER STORY THAT BEST APPLIES TO YOUR ORGANISATION/ENTITY/GROUP. PLEASE USE THE SAME FORMAT OF TITLE, USER STORY, PERSONAS, IMPORTANCE, CATEGORY.

81: Title
1000686-1000668-106360674: Comment: Accepting that operational targets will be set, looking at key areas that are particularly relevant for Funders.

82: User Story
1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

83: Personas
1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

84: Importance
1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

85: Category
1000686-1000668-106360674: [blank]

Confirming that User Stories 1 – 10, 13 and 20 specifically set out to meet funder requirement.

81: Title
1000686-1000668-105972140: Single sign on

82: User Story
1000686-1000668-105972140: As a user of the system of the system, I would like to be able to log in using my insitution's [sic] single sign on mechanism

83: Personas
1000686-1000668-105972140: User

84: Importance
1000686-1000668-105972140: Must

85: Category
1000686-1000668-105972140: [blank]

This User Story has a dependency on there being an user login to the National Open Access Monitor. This hasn't been specified as a requirement in the project or funding documentation to this point, and implementation would have additional deliverable complications. No action will be taken on single-sign on this at this time.

Appendix 7 contains the current and future open access monitoring requirements of the individual survey respondents

Current Monitoring and Reporting Requirements				
<i>id</i>	<i>Stakeholder Group</i>	<i>What metrics does your organisation/entity/group monitor or report on?</i>	<i>What metrics does your organisation/entity/group monitor or report on?</i>	<i>Data Sources</i>
1000686-1000668-106464881	Government (Research Funding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of OA publications by authors funded by [redacted] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Publisher name Journal title Corresponding author email Funder name Grant ID Funding acknowledgement from the article 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ORCID
1000686-1000668-106108416	Research Funding Organisation (Publisher)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of OA publications by projects funded by our organisation during time period X-Z 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Publication date Funder name Grant ID 	Self-reporting on Grants Management System by funded researchers
1000686-1000668-106360674	Research Funding Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Award holders: Percentage of papers in open access journals and/or on open publishing platform Award holders: Number of papers in open access journals and/or on open publishing platform Award holders: Percentage of papers published in compliant open access journals and/or on open publishing platform Award holders: Number of papers published in compliant open access journals and/or on open publishing platform Award holders: Give route of Open access: None, No, Green Route, Gold route or Open Publishing platform Award holders: Average number of peer-reviewed open access papers per award The HRB also commissions a regular bibliometrics report. 	<i>Comment: Currently restricted by available data but hoping that a national OA monitor will provide extended possibilities</i>	Bibliometrics report commissioned externally
1000686-1000668-105943931	Research Funding Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI which were published gold open access Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI 	UnPaywall

		<p>which were published green open access</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI which were published hybrid open access • Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI which were published bronze open access • Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI which were published non-open access (closed) • Number and percentage of publications funded by SFI which were published diamond open access 		
1000686-1000668-106465718	Research Funding Organisation (Research Performing)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of OA publications funded by organisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article title • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Funder name • Grant ID • Keyword 	[blank]
1000686-1000668-106407293	Research Performing Organisation	[blank]	[blank]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORCID
1000686-1000668-106487674	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of open access publications added to IR per quarter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Publication date • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • Funder ID • Grant ID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOAJ • OpenAire • ORCID • Sherpa Juliet • Sherpa Romeo
1000686-1000668-106351435	Research Performing Organisation (Service Provider)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of OA publications by authors affiliated to organisation X during time period X-Z • percentage of publications which were published open access • Annual cost of APCs for articles published by organisation via TAs • OA outputs by channel per year- green/gold/hybrid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall • Web of Science • Sci Val • [redacted] Institutional Repository

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) 	
1000686-1000668-106142071	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of OA publications by affiliated authors during specific time periods • Types of OA publications that affiliated authors are published in over time periods • % of all affiliated output in Diamond OA publications • % of all affiliated output being published under Tas • % of funded output being published in Diamond OA • % of funded output being published using TAs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author name • Co-author email • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article • Keyword 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossref • CRIS (internal) • Datacite • DOAJ • OpenAire • OpenAPC • ORCID • Scopus • Sherpa Romeo • UnPaywall
1000686-1000668-105812626	Research Performing Organisation	[blank]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Publisher name • Journal title • Co-author name 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRIS (internal) • ORCID

1000686-1000668-106108777	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total Uploads to the IR Monthly Uploads to the IR Total Downloads from the IR Monthly Downloads from the IR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRStats download stats Eprints Repository stats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CRIS (internal) Institutional Repository
1000686-1000668-106193785	Research Performing Organisation (Service Provider)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> data from Scopus and Web of Science percentage of OA publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Journal title Corresponding author name Co-author name Institution Items deposited to [redacted] (institutional repository) Scopus number of DOIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scopus Web of Science
1000686-1000668-106431246	Research Performing Organisation	[blank]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) Article License (e.g. CC-BY) Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) Publication date Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) Subject Publisher name Journal title Corresponding author name Corresponding author email Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) Co-author name Co-author email Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record Funder name Grant ID Funding acknowledgement from the article Keyword 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scopus Repository
1000686-1000668-106454728	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of OA publications by authors affiliated to our organisation during time period (typically annually) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) Article License (e.g. CC-BY) Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) Publication date Publisher name Journal title Corresponding author name Co-author name Funder ID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crossref DOAJ OpenAire ORCID Scopus Publisher-supplied data

1000686-1000668-106444422	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number and percentage of OA publications by institutional researchers broken down by bronze, green and gold OA citation performance of institutional publications by OA type 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scopus
1000686-1000668-106355712	Research Performing Organisation (Publisher)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of OA articles by journal during time period X-Z 	[blank]	[blank]
1000686-1000668-106429999	Research Performing Organisation (Publisher)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of of publications funded by [redacted] which were published hybrid open access Number of publications funded [redacted] which were published hybrid open access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) Article License (e.g. CC-BY) Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) Publication date Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) Publisher name Journal title Print ISSN Online ISSN Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) Corresponding author name Corresponding author email Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) Funder name Funding acknowledgement from the article 	[blank]
1000686-1000668-105972140	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of OA publications, including non-traditional outputs (based on RIAN categories), affiliated to [redacted] during a given time period Percentage of OA publications as a total of the publications from [redacted] in a given time period. Number of uploads to the institutional repository Number of views of items held in the institutional repository. Types of organisations which use material within our repository Number of countries that access the material within the repository SDG profile of our outputs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article title Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) Publication date Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) Subject Corresponding author email Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) Co-author email Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) Funder ID Funder name Grant ID Funding acknowledgement from the article 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CRIS (internal) Datacite DOAJ OpenAire ORCID Scopus Sherpa Juliet Sherpa Romeo UnPaywall Web of Science Digital Commons

<p>1000686-1000668-105644281</p>	<p>Research Performing Organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of OA publications by authors affiliated to [redacted] during time period X-Z, absolute number and proportion of total output. • Number of OA publications by OA type (e.g. green, gold etc.) by authors affiliated to [redacted] during time period X-Z, absolute number and proportion of total output. • Number of OA publications by authors affiliated to [redacted] during time period X-Z where the "best OA version" [unpaywall classification] is available through our institutional repository, absolute number and proportion of total. • Number of OA publications in the [redacted] institutional repository which are also available OA through another source, broken down by source (publisher OA, other repository etc), absolute number and proportion of total. • Number of OA publications by authors affiliated to [redacted] funded through OA publishing agreements (national and local) broken down by publisher, during time period X-Z- absolute number and proportion of total output. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal ID • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author name • Co-author email, Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funding acknowledgement from the article 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossref • CRIS (internal) • Datacite • Dimensions • DOAJ • ORCID • Scopus • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall • Web of Science • IReL monitoring data on OA publishing agreements
<p>1000686-1000668-106423363</p>	<p>Research Performing Organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of OA publications by authors affiliated to organisation during time periods: per three months, six months, 12 months, duration of funding agreement • percentage of publications funded by organisation, which were published open access • percentage of publications funded by organisation, which were published hybrid open access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal ID • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossref • CRIS (internal) • Scopus • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall • Web of Science

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID 	
1000686-1000668-106430385	Research Performing Organisation (Publisher)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of items from staff in a particular school/department available OA in [redacted: institutional repository] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author name • Co-author email • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article • Keyword 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossref • CRIS (internal) • DOAJ • OpenAire • ORCID • PubMed Central • Scopus • Sherpa Juliet • Sherpa Romeo • UnPaywall • Web of Science
1000686-1000668-105350481	Research Performing Organisation (Service Provider)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly additions to institutional Open Access repository • Annual downloads of documents in institutional Open Access repository • Annual e-thesis report including number of PhD theses added to repository • Annual e-thesis report on Open Access status and embargo periods in repository • Annual number of Open Access publications funded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publisher name • Journal title • Online ISSN • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Funder name 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRIS (internal) • DOAJ • ORCID • Scopus • Sherpa Romeo • Publisher-supplied data

		<p>through Transformative Agreements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of Open Access articles compared with overall output of the institution Type of Open Access articles published by the institution: Gold, Green, Brown Open Access Progress of Open Access rate of the institution over time (annually) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name of College of corresponding author Name of School of corresponding author 	
1000686-1000668-106040673	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quarterly additions to Institutional Repository for Colleges, Research Institutes and Centres for the Office of the Vice-President for Research (OVPR) Annual downloads from and full-text items on Institutional Repository available externally for SCONUL Annual PhD theses report including number of PhD theses added to Institutional Repository Dean of Graduate Studies and Graduate Studies Board Monthly report of additions to Institutional Repository for Colleges, Research Institutes and Centres and Support University Librarian 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date accessioned on Institutional Repository 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional Repository
1000686-1000668-106197179	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of publications OA by authors per year. Increase in number of OA publications year on year by authors at the institution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) Publication date Corresponding author email Co-author email Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scopus Web of Science
1000686-1000668-105501472	Service Provider (including research infrastructure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of OA publications by authors affiliated. 	<p><i>We do not need to perform a search to find this type of information - we are a smaller organisation. Researchers and authors report all OA publications to the Operations manager.</i></p>	[blank]
1000686-1000668-105333607	Service Provider (including research infrastructure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> existence of national, RPO, RFO policy on OA, for [redacted] investments at national and RPO level to support OA share of national OA publications 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> we collect information from stakeholders

<p>1000686-1000668-106387240</p>	<p>Service Provider (including research infrastructure)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of articles published open access under IReL agreements with publisher X, during time period Y-Z • number of articles published gold open access under IReL agreements with publisher X, during time period Y-Z • number of articles published hybrid open access under IReL agreements with publisher X, during time period Y-Z • number of articles published open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, which were eligible under IReL agreement but not published under IReL agreement • number of articles published gold open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, which were eligible under IReL agreement but not published under IReL agreement • number of articles published hybrid open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, which were eligible under IReL agreement but not published under IReL agreement • number of articles published closed with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, which were eligible under IReL agreement but not published under IReL agreement • number of articles published open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published gold open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published hybrid open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal ID • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article • IReL eligible journal list (https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/118jbDcYKSi mXlWkiJoOpOISC-9bS4JmnU8-JX3LIgt0/edit#gid=0) • IReL publishing agreements eligible article types https://irel.ie/open-access/ • Author eligibility verification reports (internal) • Acceptance date • Submission date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Astrophysics Data System • Bielefeld ISSN-gold dataset • Crossref • CRIS (internal) • DOAJ • EuropePMC • OpenAire • Scopus • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall • Web of Science • Funder supplied data
----------------------------------	---	---	--	---

		<p>authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance, which were not eligible under IReL agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of articles published open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article publication, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published gold open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article publication, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published hybrid open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article publication, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article submission, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published gold open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article submission, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • number of articles published hybrid open access with publisher X, during time period Y-Z, by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article submission, which were not eligible under IReL agreement • average annual number of 		
--	--	--	--	--

		<p>articles by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance with publisher X, over time period Y-Z</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • average annual number of open access articles by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance with publisher X, over time period Y-Z • average annual number of closed articles by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance with publisher X, over time period Y-Z • ratio of average annual number of open access articles by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance with publisher X, over time period Y-Z; to average annual number of closed articles by corresponding authors who were current staff/student of an IReL member organisation at the time of article acceptance with publisher X, over time period Y-Z 		
--	--	--	--	--

Future Monitoring and Reporting Requirements				
<i>id</i>	<i>Stakeholder Org</i>	<i>What metrics will your organisation/entity/group monitor or report on?</i>	<i>What data points will your organisation/entity/group use to compile those metrics?</i>	<i>Which data sources will your organisation/group/entity use to collate the data underlying the monitoring/reporting on those metrics?</i>
1000686-1000668-105796986	Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share of Irish research that is closed and open and if open, by which routes and source. • Comparison of national OA figures over time. Also with other countries if possible. • National OA analysis by HEI/RPO and sector (type of RPO). • National OA analysis by RFO. • National OA analysis by disciplines (broad categories). • Extension of the monitor to other areas of Open Science. 	[blank]	[redacted] will use the monitor

1000686-1000668-105943931	Research Funding Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and percentage of publications published gold open access. • Number and percentage of publications published green open access. • Number and percentage of publications published diamond open access. • Number and percentage of publications published hybrid open access. • Number and percentage of publications published bronze open access. • Number and percentage of publications published under a CC-BY license • Number and percentage of publications compliant with SFI's Open Access Policy • Number and percentage of publications non-compliant with SFI's Open Access Policy • Number and percentage of publications published without an embargo period within a given 12 month period • Number and percentage of publications published with an embargo period within a given 12 month period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Journal title • Journal ID • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold), • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold), • Funder ID, • Funder name, • Grant ID, • Funding acknowledgement from the article, • Keyword 	UnPaywall
1000686-1000668-106487674	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of open access publications by funder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article 	[blank]
1000686-1000668-106463438	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number/percentage of publications produced by institutional researchers which are OA, broken down by bronze, green and gold OA, or which are closed access • Breakdown of institutional OA publications by author, title, DOI, date of publication, department • percentage of institutional publications in the institutional repository • identify embargoes (current or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal ID • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossref • CRIS • Datacite • Dimensions • DOAJ • EuropePMC • OpenAire • ORCID • PubMed Central • Scopus • Sherpa Juliet • Sherpa Romeo • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall

		<p>past) on institutional publications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breakdown of institutional OA publications by funder • Location of institutional green OA – institutional repository, other? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author name • Co-author email • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article • Keyword 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web of Science
1000686-1000668-105972140	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring of preprints • Monitoring of capability to text and data mine • Automation of basic task and reports • Monitoring of APCs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Subject • Publisher name • Journal title • Journal ID • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • APC • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author name • Co-author email • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Astrophysics Data System • Bielefeld ISSN-gold dataset • Crossref • CRIS • Datacite • Delta Think • Dimensions • DOAJ • EuropePMC • OpenAire • OpenAlex • OpenAPC • ORCID • PubMed Central • ROAD • Scopus • Sherpa Juliet • Sherpa Romeo • Publisher-supplied data • UnPaywall • Web of Science

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Funder name • Grant ID • Funding acknowledgement from the article • Keyword 	
1000686-1000668-106197179	Research Performing Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OA publications by affiliation identifier • OA publications by affiliation and by funder • OA publication type • Benchmarking data • Publications without a DOI or using alternative PIDs • DOI's outside the crossref dataset • Non traditional publications. Eg datasets with datacite DOI's or Handles • Breakdown of OA types • Breakdown of license types • OA publications by SDG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Co-author email • Co-author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Co-author institution name affiliation as on the Version of Record • Co-author institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder ID • Grant ID 	[blank]
1000686-1000668-106429999	Research Performing Organisation (Publisher)	[blank]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Article title • Article Open Access type (e.g. gold, closed) • Article License (e.g. CC-BY) • Article type (e.g. original paper, review article, etc.) • Publication date • Discipline (e.g. HSS/STEM) • Publisher name • Journal title • Print ISSN • Online ISSN • Journal business model (e.g. hybrid, fully OA, subscription) • Corresponding author name • Corresponding author email • Corresponding author identifier (specify identifier, e.g. ScopusID, ORCID) • Corresponding institution ID (e.g. ROR, Ringgold) • Funder name • Funding acknowledgement from the article 	[blank]

1000686-1000668-106387240	Service Provider (including research infrastructure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of Irish publications published open access under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • number of Irish publications published gold under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • number of Irish publications published hybrid under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • number of Irish publications published open access not under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • number of Irish publications published gold not under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • number of Irish publications published hybrid not under IReL agreements during time period Y-Z • percentage of Irish publications published open access under IReL agreements / Irish publications published open access, during time period Y-Z • percentage of Irish publications published gold under IReL agreements / Irish publications published gold, during time period Y-Z • percentage of Irish publications published hybrid under IReL agreements / Irish publications published hybrid, during time period Y-Z 	[blank]	[blank]
1000686-1000668-106389035	Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of alternative outputs (such as datasets and software but not limited too) affiliated to an organisation • Number of Alternative outputs published nationally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Datacite • OpenAire • ORCID

Non-Survey Respondent: Requirements (Government):

1. Accurate;
2. Easy to use
- a. Highlights the key results, not just the granular details (e.g. x% of y [type of research] is open access; xx% of [all types of research captured by the monitor] is open access);
- b. Any associated narrative complies with the [Plain English Style Guide for the Public Service](#); and
3. Readily available to those with an internet connection (noting that public libraries facilitate internet access for those without same).